

ASSESSMENT OF WATER QUALITY AND MICROALGAL DIVERSITY IN ADICHANALLOOR POND, KOLLAM, KERALA, INDIA

N. Ratheesh*

Associate Professor, Department of Botany
Sree Narayana College, Kollam, Kerala, India

Angha Marium Shine

Department of Botany
Sree Narayana College, Kollam, Kerala, India

Navya N.S

Department of Botany
Sree Narayana College, Kollam, Kerala, India

Abstract- The present study investigated the physico-chemical characteristics of water in Adichanalloor Pond, a fresh water pond ecosystem at Kollam district, Kerala, India over a three-month period from May to July 2025 at three sampling sites. The water parameters analyzed included temperature, pH, phenolphthalein alkalinity, total alkalinity, free CO₂, dissolved oxygen (DO), biological oxygen demand (BOD), hardness, total dissolved solids (TDS), calcium, chloride, and iron using standard methods. The study resulted surface water temperature ranged from 22°C to 33°C and the pH varied across the sites, indicating acidic to slightly alkaline conditions. Total alkalinity ranged from 120 to 250 mg/L, phenolphthalein alkalinity and free CO₂ were absent. Dissolved oxygen levels ranging from 4.2 to 8.9 mg/L, while BOD showed an increasing trend reflecting higher organic pollution. The Water Quality Index (WQI) values for Sites 1, 2, and 3 were 75.91, 76.43, and 97.82 respectively, indicating poor to very poor water quality. The study revealed rich microalgal diversity in Adichanalloor Pond, identified 75 taxa from 35 families, including cyanobacteria, green algae, diatoms, desmids, and euglenoids. The dominant groups were Desmidiaceae and Naviculaceae (6 species). The presence of taxa such as *Cosmarium*, *Closterium*, and *Spirogyra* indicated good water quality, while cyanobacteria like *Oscillatoria* suggested nutrient-enriched conditions. The study indicates that Adichanalloor Pond is experiencing significant pollution caused by multiple factors, including eutrophication, human activities etc. such as bathing and washing, improper waste disposal, agricultural runoff and sewage discharge, chemical contaminants. Hence the implementation of effective pollution control and watershed management strategies are urgently required.

Key words: *Water Quality Index, dissolved oxygen, eutrophication, algal diversity*

I. INTRODUCTION

Freshwater resources in the form of surface water and groundwater constitute the principal sources of potable water worldwide [1]. Water is the fundamental to human survival, ecological balance, and sustainable socio-economic development. Its scarcity creates a serious threat to human existence. Kerala is widely recognized for its abundant natural water wealth, supported by an extensive network of rivers, wetlands, and traditional ponds. According to data from the Jal Shakti Ministry, Government of India, the state contains approximately 18,681 public ponds, many of which continue to play a crucial role in local water security. These ponds perform multiple ecological and hydrological functions, including serving as effective structures for groundwater recharge [2].

Water contamination by heavy metals has become a growing environmental concern in aquatic systems. Industrial effluents, mining activities, urban runoff, and natural processes such as weathering and atmospheric deposition contribute to the accumulation of metals in water bodies. Due to their persistent nature and ability to bioaccumulate, heavy metals pose significant risks to aquatic organisms as well as to human health through the

food chain [3]. Within aquatic ecosystems, algae have gained prominence as sensitive biological indicators due to their rapid response to changes in water chemistry and nutrient status [4]. Nevertheless, excessive algal growth can negatively affect water quality by causing unpleasant taste and odor, clogging filtration systems, forming surface scums, altering water colour, and, in some cases, producing harmful toxins. One of the most serious consequences of uncontrolled algal proliferation is eutrophication, which is typically driven by elevated nutrient inputs from agricultural runoff and wastewater discharge and results in dense phytoplankton blooms with adverse ecological effects [5].

To address increasing concerns related to water pollution, a range of regulatory frameworks and management strategies have been developed at both national and international levels [6]. Among the various assessment tools available, the Water Quality Index (WQI) has been widely adopted for evaluating the suitability of water for drinking and domestic use [7, 8]. The WQI integrates multiple physico-chemical parameters into a single numerical expression, thereby facilitating simplified interpretation and comparative assessment of water quality across different locations and time periods.

The present study was undertaken in the context of freshwater ecosystem conservation and sustainable water resource utilization. Adichanalloor Pond, a traditional freshwater body in Kollam district, Kerala, supports local biodiversity and contributes to agricultural activities and community livelihoods. In recent years, increasing anthropogenic pressures, including pollution, eutrophication, and unregulated human activities, have adversely affected the ecological condition of the pond. By examining seasonal variations in key physico-chemical parameters and microalgal diversity, the study provides essential baseline information on the ecological status of the water body. The combined application of the Water Quality Index and algal bioindicators offers an integrated framework for evaluating water quality, pollution intensity, and ecosystem resilience. The findings are expected to assist environmental planners, policymakers, and local governance institutions in developing effective strategies for the conservation and sustainable management of freshwater resources.

II. STUDY AREA AND METHODS

The present investigation was conducted in the ecologically significant freshwater body, Adichanalloor Pond, located within the semi-urban landscape of Adichanalloor village in Kollam district, Kerala. Geographically, the Pond lies at 8°53'01" N latitude and 76°42'45" E longitude, placing it within the midland agro-ecological zone of Kerala. The Pond is constructed with an area spanning approximately 2.5 acres. Though relatively small in size, Adichanalloor Pond embodies this traditional water heritage and continues to hold ecological and cultural significance in the region. The water body has a roughly quadrangular shape with shallow banks and gentle slopes, enabling easy access to water. It lies close to key civic and religious landmarks such as temples and the village office and serves as a center for ritual activities, public gatherings, and festivals, thus reinforcing its spiritual and civic importance. The study was conducted on March to June 2025. Water samples for quality analysis were collected from three different sites within the water body at regular intervals. Clean one-litre sterile plastic sampling bottles were used for sample collection. The collected samples were stored at room temperature until laboratory analysis was completed.

2.1. Methods

Water parameters such as surface water temperature, phenolphthalein alkalinity, total alkalinity, dissolved oxygen, biological oxygen demand, pH, free carbon dioxide, total hardness, total dissolved solids, chloride, calcium, phosphate, iron were measured by using the standard methods [9]. Water samples are collected monthly from multiple sites within a study area. Algal species were analysed both qualitatively and quantitatively using standard limnological methods. For quantitative studies, they were sedimented by adding Lugol's solution. The major groups of algal species such as Chlorophyceae, Cyanophyceae, Bacillariophyceae, Euglenophyceae were estimated from each sample. For qualitative study purposes, they were preserved in 4% formaldehyde solution. They were identified with the help of standard monographs and available research papers. Where necessary, photo micrograph taken with the help of camera microscope.

Water quality index and water quality status was calculated using the expression

$$WQI = \sum S_{li}$$

$$S_{li} = W_i \times Q_i$$

Where, S_{li} is the sub index of i th parameter, Q_i is the rating based on the concentration of i th parameter n , n is the number of parameters. $W_i = w_i / \sum w_i$ Where, W_i is the relative weight, w_i is the weight of each parameter. n is the number of parameters.

$$Q_i = (C_i / S_i) * 100.$$

Where, Q_i is the quality rating, C_i is the concentration of each chemical, S_i is the World Health Organization standard for each chemical parameters in milligram per litre according to the guidelines.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In the present study, the water samples taken three months from May to July 2025 at three sites of Adhichannalloor Chira, were subjected to analyse its physico-chemical and biological properties. Total alkalinity, free CO₂, total hardness, total dissolved oxygen, biological oxygen demand, chloride, calcium, iron content were analysed during the study period. The surface water temperature varied from 22-33°C with an average value of 27.5°C. The maximum temperatures of 31°C were recorded in May and minimum of 26°C was in July. During the study the average pH values were 6.38, 6.58 and 8.52 respectively from the three study sites. The average total alkalinity was 169.1 Mg/l (Fig. 1).

Dissolved oxygen concentrations exhibited notable spatial and temporal variations. Maximum DO levels were observed during July, whereas minimum values were recorded in May. The mean DO concentrations at the three sites were 5.8 mg/l, 6.8 mg/l, and 7.49 mg/l, respectively. Biological oxygen demand, an important indicator of organic pollution and microbial oxygen requirement, showed average values of 3.0 mg/l, 3.44 mg/l, and 4.0 mg/l at the respective sites. The highest BOD values were observed during July, while the lowest occurred in May. Total hardness, commonly used as an index of water quality, recorded an average concentration of 107.7 mg/l. Monthly variation in total dissolved solids (TDS) was evident, with mean values of 149.5 mg/l, 144.9 mg/l, and 300.51 mg/l at sites 1, 2, and 3, respectively. The available calcium concentration analysis revealed an overall mean value of 132.9 mg/l, with peak levels observed during May at all sites. Chloride concentration was also highest in May, registering an average value of 21 mg/l. Iron concentrations recorded mean values of 0.5 mg/l, 1.28 mg/l, and 1.56 mg/l, at sites 1, 2, and 3, respectively (Fig. 1).

Water temperature plays a crucial role in regulating the solubility of gases, particularly dissolved oxygen and carbon dioxide. Several earlier studies have reported an inverse relationship between temperature and dissolved oxygen concentration [10,11,12]. In the present study, reduced DO levels were observed during the summer months, which may be attributed to elevated water temperatures that lower oxygen solubility and increased microbial decomposition of organic matter consuming available oxygen [13]. The concentration of free CO₂ in aquatic systems is also influenced by temperature [14]. However free CO₂ was absent at all study sites, preventing the establishment of any temperature-related trend.

Total alkalinity is an important parameter for evaluating the productivity potential of aquatic ecosystems. Water bodies with alkalinity values exceeding 90 mg/l are generally considered productive [15]. The alkalinity values recorded in the present study indicate favourable conditions for biological productivity. Although TDS concentrations in Indian inland waters may range up to 2416 mg/l [16], excessive TDS can impose osmotic stress on aquatic organisms and reduce light penetration, thereby suppressing photosynthetic activity [17]. In the present study, TDS values ranged from 120–200 mg/l at site 1, 100–190 mg/l at site 2, and 250–400 mg/l at site 3 (Fig 1).

Hydrogen ion concentration (pH) is widely regarded as a critical indicator of water quality and ecosystem productivity [18]. Each aquatic organism has an optimal pH range for growth and survival [19, 20, 21, 22]. The decline in pH observed during the monsoon season can be attributed to dilution caused by heavy rainfall and freshwater inflow. In the present investigation, pH values ranged from 6.3 to 8.5, remaining within the

permissible limits prescribed by ICMR [23]. Although higher alkalinity may indicate pollution [24], the recorded alkalinity values were well within the permissible limit of 600 mg L^{-1} recommended by WHO [25].

Micronutrients such as calcium exhibited higher concentrations during the pre-monsoon period and lower values during the monsoon season across all sampling sites, supporting earlier findings [26]. Chloride levels were comparatively lower during the rainy season and higher during the pre-monsoon period, reflecting eutrophication trends [27]. The chloride concentrations recorded were within permissible limits specified by BIS [28], ICMR [23], and WHO [25]. However, iron concentrations at all three sites exceeded the BIS [28] desirable limit of 0.3 mg L^{-1} . Iron, though essential for phytoplankton photosynthesis [29], can become problematic at elevated concentrations, leading to staining and deterioration of water quality [30].

Figure 1. Monthly variation in water parameters

The quality rating scale for each parameter was calculated by dividing its concentration in each water sample by its respective standards and multiplied the results by 100. The method has been widely used by the various scientists [31,32,33,34]. The standard values are given in the Table. 1.

Table 1. Standard values of Water quality index

Water quality Index Level	Water Quality status
0-25	Excellent water quality
26-50	Good water quality
51-75	Poor water quality
76-100	Very poor water quality
>100	Unsuitable for drinking

Eight water quality parameters viz pH, alkalinity, hardness, TDS, DO, BOD, Chloride, from were used for the calculations of water quality index of Adichanalloorpond. The water quality index values of the three sites were 75.91, 76.43, 97.82 at site 1, 2, 3 respectively. The concept of indices to represent gradation in water quality was first proposed by Horton in 1965. WQI is measure of overall quality of water which has been statistically arrived from a number of parameters and is in use more to describe the quality of freshwater systems [35].

Algae serve as primary producers in aquatic ecosystems [36] and act as primary colonizers in soil environments due to their photosynthetic capabilities [37]. The water samples were examined microscopically to identify the microalgae. In the present study, a total of 75 algal taxa belonging to 35 families, mostly of cyanobacteria (blue-green algae), green algae (Chlorophyta), diatoms (Bacillariophyceae), and desmids (Desmidiaceae), along with some euglenoids (Euglenophyta). These are typically observed in freshwater ecosystems and are indicators of water quality, productivity, and ecosystem health. All the taxa were enumerated and shown in Table 2. It is found that Desmidiaceae family is the dominant one with 14 species followed by Naviculaceae with 6 species and Chroococcaceae, Oscillatoriaceae and Closteriaceae with five species each. From the study some relatively rare or unique taxa were obtained. They are *Synura uvella* (Family- Synuraceae), *Elakatothrix acuta* (Elakatothricaceae), *Oocystis borgei* (Chlorellaceae) and *Chlorobotrys regularis* (Chlorobotryaceae). This algal floristic list suggests a diverse phytoplankton community in the present study. Presence of diatoms, desmids, and green algae like *Cosmarium*, *Closterium* indicates clean or moderately clean water. Cyanobacteria like *Microcystis*, *Oscillatoria* are found in potential green water. Whereas Cyanobacteria and green algae are often associated with nitrogen/phosphate rich water. However rich taxonomic diversity reflects ecological stability and a variety of microhabitats in the water body.

Table 2 Algal taxa isolated and identified during the study

Sl no.	Name of the taxa	Family
1	<i>Chroococcus pallidus</i>	Chroococcaceae
2	<i>Chroococcusturgidus</i>	Chroococcaceae
3	<i>Aphanocapsa delicatissima</i>	Chroococcaceae
4	<i>Gleocapsa calcarata</i>	Chroococcaceae
5	<i>Gleocapsa alpina</i>	Chroococcaceae
6	<i>Chlorococcum infusionum</i>	Chlorococcaceae
7	<i>Chlorococcus minutus</i>	Chlorococcaceae
8	<i>Zygnema</i> sp.	Zygnemataceae
9	<i>Spirogyra</i> sp.	Zygnemataceae
10	<i>Pandorina</i> sp.	Volvocaceae
11	<i>Ulothrix</i> sp.	Ulotrichaceae
12	<i>Synedraacus</i>	Ulnariaceae
13	<i>Tabellaria</i> sp.	Tabellariaceae
14	<i>Synura uvella</i>	Synuraceae
15	<i>Cyclotella</i> sp.	Stephanodiscaceae
16	<i>Ankistrodesmus spinosum</i>	Selenastraceae
17	<i>Selenastrum bibrarianum</i>	Selenastraceae
18	<i>Scytonema</i> sp.	Scytonemaceae
19	<i>Desmodesmus armatus</i>	Scenedesmaceae
20	<i>Coelastrum reticulatum</i>	Scenedesmaceae
21	<i>Coelastrum indicum</i>	Scenedesmaceae
22	<i>Scenedesmus quadricauda</i>	Scenedesmaceae
23	<i>Rhopalodiagibba</i>	Rhopalodiaceae
24	<i>Phormidium tenue</i>	Oscillatoriaceae
25	<i>Oscillatoria limosa</i>	Oscillatoriaceae
26	<i>Oscillatoria furmosa</i>	Oscillatoriaceae
27	<i>Lyngbyamojoor</i>	Oscillatoriaceae
28	<i>Lyngbya lutea</i>	Oscillatoriaceae
29	<i>Oedogonium</i> sp.	Oedogoniaceae
30	<i>Nostoc caeruleum</i>	Nostocaceae
31	<i>Anabena</i> sp.	Nostocaceae
32	<i>Haslea ostrearia</i>	Naviculaceae
33	<i>Naviculacinctata</i>	Naviculaceae
34	<i>Naviculacryptocephala</i>	Naviculaceae
35	<i>Naviculacuspadata</i>	Naviculaceae
36	<i>Pinnularia conica</i>	Naviculaceae

37	<i>Pinnulariabrevicosa</i>	Naviculaceae
38	<i>Microcystis viridis</i>	Microcystaceae
39	<i>Netriumdigitus</i>	Mesotaeniaceae
40	<i>Spirotaeniacondensata</i>	Mesotaeniaceae
41	<i>Merismopediatrolleri</i>	Merismopediaceae
42	<i>Pediastrum tetras</i>	Hydrodictyceae
43	<i>Pediastrum</i> sp.	Hydrodictyceae
44	<i>Gomphonemaconstrictum</i>	Gomphonemataceae
45	<i>Phacussp.</i>	Euglenaceae
46	<i>Trachelomonassp.</i>	Euglenaceae
47	<i>Elakatothrix acuta</i>	Elakatotrichaceae
48	<i>Spaerozozsmafiliforme</i>	Desmidiaceae
49	<i>Cosmarium perforatum</i>	Desmidiaceae
50	<i>Cosmariumquadrum</i>	Desmidiaceae
51	<i>Cosmariummoniliforme</i>	Desmidiaceae
52	<i>Cosmariumtetrachondrum</i>	Desmidiaceae
53	<i>Cosmariumreniforme</i>	Desmidiaceae
54	<i>Cosmarium corda</i>	Desmidiaceae
55	<i>Staurodesmusconvergens</i>	Desmidiaceae
56	<i>Spondylosiumjavanicum</i>	Desmidiaceae
57	<i>Eustrummansatum</i>	Desmidiaceae
58	<i>Desmidium elegans</i>	Desmidiaceae
59	<i>Micrasteria furcata</i>	Desmidiaceae
60	<i>Hyalotheca mucosa</i>	Desmidiaceae
61	<i>Staurastrum alternans</i>	Desmidiaceae
62	<i>Cymbellaaffinis</i>	Cymbellaceae
63	<i>Closterium setaceum</i>	Closteriaceae
64	<i>Closterium moniliferum</i>	Closteriaceae
65	<i>Closterium praelongum</i>	Closteriaceae
66	<i>Closterium didymotocum</i>	Closteriaceae
67	<i>Closterium incurvum</i>	Closteriaceae
68	<i>Cladophora</i> sp.	Cladophoraceae
69	<i>Rhizocloniumhieroglyphicum</i>	Cladophoraceae
70	<i>Chlorobotrysregularis</i>	Chlorobotryaceae
71	<i>Oocystisborgei</i>	Chlorellaceae
72	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Chlorellaceae
73	<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	Chlamydomonadaceae
74	<i>Nitzchia palea</i>	Bacillariaceae
75	<i>Nitzchia</i> sp.	Bacillariaceae

Algae can persist under a wide range of environmental conditions, including variations in salinity, temperature, light intensity, and pH. Consequently, algal investigations play a vital role in evaluating the biological potential as well as the ecological and economic status of aquatic ecosystems [38, 39, 40]. Analyses of algal species composition and diversity provide valuable insights into aquatic ecosystem functioning and support the sustainable management of water resources for future generations [41, 42, 43, 44]. Researchers have documented the occurrence and distribution of Chlorococcales in freshwater environments, emphasizing the influence of temperature on their abundance. Researchers like Shaheen [45] reported that lower temperature regimes are generally unfavourable for Chlorococcales, whereas higher temperatures promote their proliferation. Similarly, Nandan and Patel [46] observed that Chlorococcales attain maximum abundance in tropical water bodies under elevated temperature conditions. In contrast, studies by Puttaiah and Somashekar [47], Hegde and Karanth [48], and Banatwala et al. [49] suggested that water temperature is not a decisive factor governing the growth of desmids.

The present investigation revealed the dominance of algal taxa including *Navicula*, *Closterium*, *Cosmarium*, and *Cymbella*. Water samples further showed the prevalence of filamentous green algae such as *Spirogyra*, *Cladophora*, and *Oedogonium*. In addition, a diverse assemblage comprising *Oscillatoria*, *Gomphonema*, *Synura*, *Zygnema*, *Rhizoclonium*, *Ankistrodesmus*, *Phormidium*, *Pinnularia*, *Phacus*, *Nitzschia*, *Synedra*, *Lynngbya*, *Micrasterias*, *Selenastrum*, and *Chlorella* was recorded. Seasonal variation in microalgal community composition was also evident. During the pre-monsoon period, diatoms along with *Scenedesmus* and *Closterium* were dominant, whereas post-monsoon samples exhibited increased representation of taxa such as *Microcystis*, *Synura*, and *Oscillatoria*. Researchers like Palmer [50] identified genera such as *Oscillatoria*, *Euglena*, *Scenedesmus*, *Chlamydomonas*, *Navicula*, *Nitzschia*, and *Ankistrodesmus* as characteristic indicators of organically polluted waters. Supporting this observation, Ratnasabapathy[51] reported *Oscillatoria*, *Euglena*, *Chlorella*, and *Ankistrodesmus* as typical components of heavily polluted aquatic habitats.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The study concludes that Adichanallor pond is undergoing increasing pollution due to various anthropogenic pressures, including agricultural runoff, domestic waste discharge, eutrophication, and poor waste management. The significant correlation between chemical parameters and dissolved oxygen levels further emphasizes the need for urgent action. Therefore, regular water quality monitoring, public awareness, effective pollution control, and sustainable management practices are essential to preserve the ecological integrity of Adichanallor Pond.

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